

SPECIAL HELP NEEDED CHILD CATEGORIES

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Abstract: Severe, abrupt changes observed in the physical or mental development of children with developmental disabilities have a negative impact on the formation of the child's personality. Therefore, special conditions must be created for the upbringing and education of such children, that is, they must receive education in specially specialized preschool educational institutions and schools or among their normally developed peers and, if necessary, on the basis of special programs. and textbooks... we need to learn and educate ourselves.

Key words: mental retardation, autism, infection, intoxication, phenylketonuria, Down syndrome, asphyxia, smallpox, plague, typhoid, cholera, trachoma, measles.

In the science of clinical foundations of special pedagogy, work is carried out with different categories of children who need special support: These are:

- 1) children with hearing impairments (deaf, hard of hearing children, late-deafened children);
- 2) children with visual impairments (blind, visually impaired children);
- 3) mentally retarded oligophrenic children;
- 4) children with severe speech defects;
- 5) children with musculoskeletal disorders;
- 6) mentally retarded children.
- 7) children with complex multiple developmental defects;
- 8) children with autism syndrome.

Children with developmental disabilities should be raised and educated among their normally developed peers in inclusive education or in specialized educational institutions. Only defects that greatly affect the overall development of the child can be grounds for considering him or her a child in need of special support. For example, if a child hears only with his left ear, but this defect does not affect his overall development, he studies at school on an equal basis with his peers, he does not belong to the category of children in need of special help. Adults cannot be considered in need of special help if defects that arise for certain reasons do not affect their overall development.

A defect observed in a child with any developmental disorder may be associated with organic or functional changes in the central or peripheral nervous system.

Various deficiencies in the development of a child can also appear as a result of an unfavorable environment, improper upbringing and education. For example, unfavorable family conditions, pedagogical negligence, incorrect attitude of the teacher towards the child and many other reasons negatively affect the development of the child, make him unable to master the program materials well and fall into the number of unsuccessful students. It will become sloppy. Nevertheless, we do not classify such a child as a child in need of special help, since his developmental defects are not caused by any organic or functional pathological changes in the body, but are caused by other reasons.

Parents, guardians and teachers must be able to distinguish these children from children with special needs.

For reasons of occurrence, any developmental defect can be congenital or acquired through marriage.

Congenital defects largely depend on the health and living conditions of the expectant mother. The development of the fetus in the womb can be affected by infections, intoxications, injuries and other factors. The mother may suffer from various diseases during pregnancy, take various medications unknowingly and cause the birth of a child with defects.

Birth defects can also be caused by genetic factors. For example, there are also hearing and visual impairments, transmission of mental retardation from generation to child (phenylketonuria, Down syndrome, Rh incompatibility, etc.). Parental alcoholism, drug addiction and addiction can also cause the birth of a child with defects.

Defects acquired in marriage arise as a result of the influence of harmful factors on the child's body during birth and in subsequent periods. During childbirth, brain damage, entanglement of the umbilical cord and suffocation of the child (asphyxia), etc. can sometimes lead to a developmental defect.

The development of defects can also be caused by a child suffering from various diseases at an early age (up to three years), such as meningitis, meningoencephalitis, otitis media, damage to the central nervous system and other similar diseases.

Our country is taking many measures to prevent defects in the physical or mental development of children, and significant progress has been achieved in this area. In Uzbekistan, the number of children in need of special care has decreased due to the expansion of treatment and preventive care for the population and great achievements in the field of medicine. There are cases where children need special care due to smallpox, plague, typhoid, cholera,

trachoma, measles and other infectious diseases specific to children. Due to hereditary factors, as well as intoxication and other reasons leading to damage to the brain and analyzers during the formation of the body, there are still cases when a child needs special help.

Does a mother's diet during pregnancy affect the child's development? The child receives the necessary substances from the mother's body during life in the womb, so it is believed that this influence is not of great importance. But the disease of an anemic mother, who has been ill for a long time, affects the child in the womb. During the first 3-4 months of pregnancy, the mother has scarlet fever, rubella and other filtering viral diseases, toxoplasmosis, listeriosis, wound infection, congenital heart disease, cleft lip (cleft lip), cleft palate (cleft palate). low), it has been proven that there are six fingers on the legs and arms, a hole between the vertebrae, and a protrusion of the spinal cord into it (spina bibida) and other birth defects.

It has been proven that if you regulate the care and feeding of very premature babies, they will soon catch up with their peers and will not move away from them in the future. Some childhood diseases, in particular congenital and acquired after birth diseases, block the growth and development of children, congenital heart defects, congenital and acquired brain lesions, children usually lag behind their peers in growth and development.

In addition to the nervous system, the endocrine apparatus (neurohumoral factor) is also important for the proper physical and mental development of the child.

A fetus that develops normally in the womb can be exposed to various harmful influences. This can lead to abnormal fetal development and even birth defects. At the same time , the fetal nervous system begins to form, and any harmful effects will damage its physical and mental appearance. Abnormal conditions in children - physical weakness, mental retardation, lack of speech development - are mainly the result of harmful influences before birth and injuries during childbirth. Therefore, a healthy child will be born only when every woman pays attention to her health during pregnancy.

The main causes of abnormal development - previously, children with any abnormal condition were considered hereditary. Due to the lack of deep knowledge about the laws of heredity, even tuberculosis, injuries, various mental illnesses, alcoholism and hakoza were considered a disease passed on from generation to generation, that is, a pathological period. Some authors mistakenly believe that diseases such as deafness and mental retardation are the

result of pathological heredity. Because there were no methods for the practical study of hereditary diseases. In the psychiatric clinic there was also a theory of a genetic disorder or degeneration.

According to this theory, any normally living family or generation begins to fall apart after a certain period of time.

A sign of such nausea is the birth in a family of children who are disabled, short, epileptic, or mentally retarded. Of course, modern scientific progress has put an end to such a theory. Currently, all kinds of diseases associated with heredity are being studied and analyzed very deeply. Wounds, tuberculosis, chronic alcoholism and similar diseases are not considered hereditary. Children born to parents with ulcers and similar diseases, but treated promptly, may not have symptoms of ulcers. Wound-forming spirochete microbes are not detected in the blood of such children. Children of alcoholic parents will never necessarily become alcoholics. However, in some cases, these children may experience symptoms of lethargy, mental retardation and mental retardation. These symptoms are not a sign of heredity, but a consequence of the development of the fetus in a somewhat weak and unfavorable environment as a result of harmful influences on the parents. Every parent should keep in mind that his diseases or illnesses can be transmitted to the fetus very early and this condition will certainly affect the health of the unborn child. Damage to the fetal brain caused by exposure to food or various harmful gases, eating dishes, fasting, as well as radical actions of pregnant women to get rid of the fetus (abortion). Along with the study and analysis of various anomalies in the development of the nervous system caused by the influence of the external environment, an in-depth study of some internal factors (endocrine) depending on heredity is necessary. In this regard, in the teachings of heredity, much attention is paid to the importance of nucleic acids that preserve signs of heredity and transmit them from generation to generation (RNA, DNA factors).

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